

Potential Fungicidal Compounds. Part III*. Some Halogenonitrophenyl and -naphthyl Esters of Piperidino- and Morpholino-dithiocarbamic Acids

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Several halogenonitrophenyl, and -naphthyl esters of piperidino- and morpholino-dithiocarbamic acids have been prepared with a view to testing their fungicidal and insecticidal activities. Structures of some of these compounds have also been established.

Several halogenonitrophenyl esters of *NN*-diethyldithiocarbamic acid have recently been found to possess fungicidal activity, particularly against *Tricophyton mentagrophytes*, *Microsporum canis*, and *Aspergillus niger*¹. Also 2,4-di- and 2,4,6-tri-nitrophenyl esters of piperidino- and morpholino-dithiocarbamic acids are known to have strong fungicidal activity against *Sclerotinia fructicola*². It was therefore considered worthwhile to synthesise a number of halogenonitro-phenyl-, tolyl, and -naphthyl analogues of these esters and to screen them for fungicidal and insecticidal activities.

These esters were obtained by the condensation of halogenopolynitrobenzenes with sodium salts of piperidino- (Table I) and morpholino-dithiocarbamic acids (Table II). In the case of 1,2,5-trihalogeno-4,6-dinitrobenzenes, the substitution took place at the 1-position. Thus 1,2,5-trichloro (or 2,5-dichloro-1-bromo) -4,6-dinitrobenzene, when condensed with sodium salt of piperidino- and morpholino-dithiocarbamic acids, furnished 3,6-dichloro-2,4-dinitrophenyl esters of piperidino- and morpholino-dithiocarbamic acid respectively.

Structures of the esters obtained from 1,2,3-trichloro- and 1,3-dichloro-2-bromo-4,6-dinitrobenzenes are based on the previous observation¹ that only one of the halogens takes part in the condensation when molecular quantities of the halogenonitrobenzene and sodium salt of *N*-substituted dithiocarbamic acid are used.

The fungicidal and insecticidal activities of these compounds will be published elsewhere.

EXPERIMENTAL

Sodium Salt of Piperidinodithiocarbamic Acid.—To a cooled solution (5-10°) of NaOH (5 g.) in water (5 ml) and methanol (25 ml) a solution of piperidine (10.5 g.) in methanol

*The note published in the May issue of this Journal is to be treated as Part I of the series.

1. Garg, *This Journal*, 1965, 42, 839.

2. Krack and Stota, *Coll. Czech. Chem. Comm.*, 1963, 28, 3159.

TABLE I

Halogenonitrophenyl and -naphthyl esters of piperidinodithiocarbamic acid.

S. No.	Halogenonitrobenzene.	R.	M.P.	Yield.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.		% Sulphur.	
						Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
1	1-Chloro-3,6-dinitro-	3,6-Di-NP	119°	75%	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ O ₄ N ₃ S ₂	13.03	12.84	19.46	19.57
2	1,3-Dichloro-4,6-dinitro-	6-Chloro-3,4-di-NP	131°	80°	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ O ₄ N ₃ Cl ₂ S ₂	11.58	11.63	17.66	17.70
3	1-Chloro-2-bromo-4,6-dinitro-	6-Bromo-3,4-di-NP	185-86°	83	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ O ₄ N ₃ BrS ₂	10.29	10.34	15.69	15.76
4	1-Chloro-2-iodo-4,6-dinitro-	6-Iodo-3,4-di-NP	175-76°	86	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ O ₄ N ₃ IS ₂	9.32	9.27	14.04	14.13
5	1,3-Dichloro-4,6-dinitro-	3-Chloro-3,4-di-NP	106°	85	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ O ₄ N ₃ ClS ₂	11.51	11.63	17.65	17.70
6	1,4-Dichloro-2,6-dinitro-	4-Chloro-3,6-di-NP	169°	80	"	11.57	11.63	17.60	17.70
7	1-Chloro-4,6-dinitro-2-methyl-	6-Methyl-3,4-di-NP	136°	70	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ O ₄ N ₃ S ₂	13.11	13.33	19.99	19.77
8	1-Chloro-4,6-dinitro-3-methyl-	5-Methyl-3,4-di-NP	98-99°	75	"	12.40	12.32	18.71	18.77
9	1-Chloro-2,6-dinitro-4-methyl-	4-Methyl-2,6-di-NP	137°	65	"	12.39	12.32	18.68	18.77
10	1-Chloro-2,4,6-trinitro-5-methyl-	5-Methyl-2,4,6-tri-NP	129-30°	80	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ O ₄ N ₄ S ₂	14.42	14.51	16.49	16.56
11	1,2,3-Trichloro-4,6-dinitro-	5,6-Dichloro-3,4-di-NP	144°	85	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ O ₄ N ₃ Cl ₃ S ₂	10.98	10.61	16.04	16.16
12	3-Chloro-1,3-dibromo-4,6-dinitro-	5,6-Dichloro-3,4-di-NP	157°	80	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ O ₄ N ₃ Cl ₂ Br ₂ S ₂	9.95	9.53	14.60	14.53
13	1,3-Dichloro-4,6-dinitro-5-methyl-	5-Bromo-6-chloro-3,4-di-NP	129°	75	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ O ₄ N ₃ Cl ₂ BrS ₂	11.04	11.19	17.43	17.04
14	1,3-Dichloro-4,6-dinitro-2-methyl-	5-Chloro-6-methyl-3,4-di-NP	125°	65	"	11.28	11.16	16.98	17.04
15	1,2,5-Trichloro-4,6-dinitro-	3,6-Dichloro-2,4-di-NP	163°	70	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ O ₄ N ₃ Cl ₃ S ₂	10.42	10.61	16.04	16.16
16	2,5-Dichloro-1-bromo-4,6-dinitro-	Do	163°	66	"	10.39	10.61	16.33	16.16
17	1-Chloro-2,4-dinitro-naphthalene	2,4-Dinitronaphthyl	154°	80	C ₁₀ H ₇ O ₄ N ₂ S ₂	11.09	11.14	16.89	16.98

* All melting points are uncorrected.
NP denotes nitrophenyl.

(20 ml) was added with stirring. It was then cooled to 2-5° and CS₂ (9.4 g.) was added to it dropwise with stirring during 60 min. The resulting suspension was stirred for 35 min. more and the separated sodium salt of piperidinodithiocarbamic acid was filtered, dried, and crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 285° (decomp.). (Found: S, 34.78. Calc. for C₆H₁₀NS₂Na: S, 34.97%).

Sodium Salt of Morpholinodithiocarbamic Acid.—Morpholine (8.7 g.), dissolved in ethanol (10 ml), was added with stirring to a cooled solution of NaOH (4 g.) in water (5 ml) and ethanol (15 ml). The resulting solution was cooled to 5-10° and CS₂ (7.6 g.) was added to it dropwise with stirring during 45 min. The suspension, thus obtained, was further stirred for 60 min., maintaining the temperature below 10°. Sodium salt of morpholinodithiocarbamic acid separating as white crystals was filtered and recrystallised from methanol, m.p. 300° (decomp.). (Found: S, 34.59. Calc. for C₅H₉ONS₂Na: S, 34.37%).

TABLE II

Halogenonitrophenyl and -naphthyl esters of morpholinodithiocarbamic acid.

M.P.	Yield.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.		% Sulphur.	
			Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
144°	78%	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₅ N ₃ S ₂	12.61	12.77	19.39	19.45
145°	84	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₅ N ₃ ClS ₂	11.49	11.55	17.49	17.61
231°	80	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₅ N ₃ BrS ₂	10.40	10.29	15.60	15.69
195°	84	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₅ N ₃ IS ₂	9.44	9.23	14.21	14.07
137°	80	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₅ N ₃ ClS ₂	11.36	11.55	17.58	17.61
212°	85	"	11.61	11.55	17.42	17.61
158°	80	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ O ₅ N ₃ S ₂	12.09	12.24	18.53	18.66
126°	85	"	12.31	12.24	18.59	18.66
151°	70	"	12.18	12.24	18.44	18.66
107°	75	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ O ₇ N ₄ S ₂	14.26	14.43	16.28	16.49
169°	88	C ₁₁ H ₉ O ₅ N ₃ Cl ₂ S ₂	10.67	10.55	16.20	16.08
160°	75	C ₁₁ H ₉ O ₅ N ₃ ClBrS ₂	9.36	9.49	14.51	14.46
159°	60	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ O ₅ N ₃ ClS ₂	11.24	11.13	16.99	16.95
164°	77	"	11.16	11.13	16.82	16.95
123°	75	C ₁₁ H ₉ O ₅ N ₃ Cl ₂ S ₂	10.48	10.55	16.13	16.08
123°	80	"	10.62	10.55	16.01	16.08
167°	87	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ O ₅ N ₃ S ₂	11.14	11.08	16.73	16.89

N. B. Numbers of halogenonitrobenzenes and R are the same as in Table I.

Phenyl and Naphthyl Esters of Piperidino- and Morpholino-dithiocarbamic Acids.—A solution of the respective halogenonitrobenzene or -naphthalene (0.01M, 25% soln.) in ethanol was added dropwise with stirring to a solution of sodium salt of

piperidino- or morpholino-dithiocarbamic acid (0.01M, 40% soln.) in dilute ethanol, cooled to 2-5° during 45 min. The reaction mixture was further stirred at the same temperature and the product separating was filtered, washed with water, and crystallised from anhydrous ethanol. The esters obtained are shining yellow or orange crystalline compounds; these are readily soluble in acetone, insoluble in water, and sparingly soluble in methanol and ethanol.

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